

TRAJECTORY MODELLING OF PUBLISHING COSTS USING OPEN RESEARCH INFORMATION

An open source analytics pipeline

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using Open Research Information
- An open source analytics pipeline**

Preprint

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ABSTRACT

Financial modelling is central to strategic planning for future investments in scholarly communications systems. While internal planning within purchasing consortia and national systems has always involved scenario modeling and financial analysis this can be restricted by access to relevant data and necessarily confidential while planning and negotiating of arrangements is in place. This limits the capacity for informed community discussions of future scenarios.

Through a project initially supported by IReL and building from previous work undertaken by the Curtin Open Knowledge Initiative and Invest in Open Infrastructure, we have built a system for examining the costs of potential future scenarios, based on cost parameters calculated from available data. In this analysis we use the example of the Council of Australasian University Librarians (CAUL, the Australia-Aotearoa New Zealand library consortium) and Bibsam (the Swedish library consortium) to demonstrate a system that implements this analysis.

An important question that arises is the degree to which such analysis is possible with purely public data. We show how publicly available bibliographic metadata can be used to build publishing profiles as well as the possibilities and limitations of public data on the outputs of publishing agreements and publishing services costs. Our analysis shows that where such data is made available a full detailed analysis is possible and how the analysis shown here could be generalised. We commend CAUL and Bibsam for their commitment to transparency and call for other consortia to work towards making more of the detailed information relating to publishing services publicly accessible to support wider community analysis and conversations.

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BACKGROUND

Many of the flash points of debate around scholarly communication relate to costs. From the serials crisis of the 1990s and early 2000s to the hopes that open access would reduce costs, through debates over so-called “transformative” agreements and the exclusionary effects of APCs to the apparent removal of publishing charges as an allowable cost for NIH grants, money has always been an issue at the centre of tensions.

At the same time high quality information and analysis on costs, pricing and return on investment has been limited. While the secrecy enforced by non-disclosure agreements around subscriptions and publishing agreements has receded somewhat, detailed information on what is spent, and with which publishers is at best patchy. Reporting frameworks such as OpenAPC, ESAC and consortial disclosures partially fill the gap but detailed information, particularly at the level of individual outputs and institutional investments in repositories and infrastructures is limited.

From macro to meso to micro-levels

Most analysis in the public domain has been at the level of systems. Estimates of the size of the scholarly communication market have varied but various reports have sought to define the overall scale and divide that into its various contributing portions (e.g. Jubb et al., 2017, Lefèvre et al. 2020, Kemp and Skinner, 2024). Market-focused analysis has however largely neglected small and no-cost publishing options. The scale of provision of low- and zero-cost journal publishing options (including repository infrastructure) remains very difficult to determine although recent estimates converge on around 20,000 journals (Bosman et al. 2021, Laakso and Taskin, 2025).

Individual publishers, mostly those with reporting obligations due to stock market listing or non-profit status, do report some levels of information, but generally in ways that obscure important details of how different revenue streams are performing. Library consortia and individual research institutions provide some public reporting, but this differs substantially between consortia and countries. The high-stakes nature of negotiations with publishers is often used as an argument to justify some level of secrecy. While confidentiality is reasonable during a negotiation the release of information after negotiations are concluded can also be patchy. For instance, even where agreements are released they often do not provide details of costs (European Commission, 2024), and updates to agreements or supplementary payments are rarely made public.

At the level of individual outputs initiatives such as OpenAPC¹ and the openCost consortium² have made substantial progress on providing systems that allow detailed reporting and

¹ <https://www.openapc.net>

² <https://opencost.de/news/en/project/>

exchange of information. However, contributions to these have uneven coverage and are limited to contributions from specific institutions. In particular, information on the inclusion of specific articles within publishing agreements is extremely limited. List of articles that are published under agreements are routinely provided by publishers to consortia, but these are generally treated as internal information and not made publicly available. .

There are exceptions and exemplars that achieve high levels of transparency and quality of public information. Amongst these, the Swedish library consortium Bibsam is a standout example, providing regular public data on expenditure and articles included within agreements, and sharing publisher contracts publicly. The Council of Australasian University Librarians (CAUL, the Australia-Aotearoa New Zealand library consortium) also has a dataset on articles published within agreements. However the details of publisher contracts, including expenditure, are not publicly available.

Modelling with public and open data

Developing models to analyse existing expenditures and model future scenarios requires information on the set of outputs in scope, the current set of expenditures and the services they are incurred for. In practice, where this information is available it is released in different forms and from different sources in different settings. We use public and open bibliographic datasets to define a set of outputs, based on affiliation data for a specified set of organisations; data on publishing service agreements and the costs incurred; and data on specific services provided, most importantly whether specific outputs are covered by publishing agreements. In this work by “costs” we mean the costs incurred by organisations purchasing services associated with the publishing system. We acknowledge that there is a distinction to be made between prices charged and cost incurred by publishers and other publishing service providers but here we are concerned with the *overall costs* experienced by the research organisations.

Identifying outputs

To identify outputs in scope using public and open data we first need to specify the set of organisations. We use a list of Research Organisation Registry (ROR) identifiers to then query both OpenAlex and OpenAIRE data resources for relevant outputs. Open data sources are a significant growing area with a shift from traditional proprietary data sources underway. These data sources are developing rapidly meaning that analysis of their completeness and coverage is often out of date as soon as it is published.

Broadly speaking these data sources are more inclusive, covering a larger set of research outputs. As a result they also tend to have less complete metadata and overall contain more errors in metadata. However they are also accessible and openly licensed, making analyses more reproducible and auditable. At the level of aggregation we are working at, previous analyses show that results are broadly comparable to those based on proprietary data sources. For

instance, the Leiden Ranking Open Edition captures a much larger set of outputs than the older edition based on Web of Science data, but produces broadly comparable results. In this work we elected to combine the two largest sets of open bibliographic metadata, OpenAlex and OpenAIRE to maximise coverage and inclusion. We use full data snapshots provided in the community ORION-DBs resources³.

Output level costs and data

The relative paucity of comprehensive data has led to multiple efforts seeking to aggregate data sources together to support analysis. Some reporting frameworks, of which the most significant are OpenAPC and the openCost projects provide mechanisms for collating information on publication expenditure at the output level. These projects both initially focused on recording payments of processing charges for journal articles but are expanding to cover inclusion of outputs within publishing agreements, and other forms of output including books. Specific countries have a high degree of engagement with these projects including Germany, Sweden and the Netherlands but coverage remains limited globally.

Other efforts to define publishing costs have focused on providing data on list price APCs. Amongst these Walt Crawford's Gold Open Access Publishing as part of a larger analysis of full open access journals, provides a yearly list of APCs by journal (Crawford, 2016 to Crawford, 2025). These are drawn from the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ). DOAJ provides up to date but not longitudinal data. Crawford's registry is therefore useful here.

Another substantial effort is that driven by the ScholCommLab in Canada which provides a large scale dataset of journal list prices APCs over time for a significant set of journals. The focus of this data aggregation prioritised large publishers, as this provided the most efficient means of estimating market scale. Haustein et al. (2024), building on previous work (Butler et al, 2023), show the overall scale of the market is substantial with estimated expenditures of \$US8.4B from 2019 to 2023. In parallel work, van Bellen et al. (2025) also argued the importance of looking beyond traditional bibliometric sources to gain a full view of the publishing landscape..

There is a range of estimates at the per-output level for non-APC ("Diamond") open access. In the 2021 Open Access Diamond Journals Study (OADJS), average costs were estimated at €483 per article, based on self-reporting of total annual costs by 965 diamond journals (Bosman et al., 2021). This corresponds well with the estimated cost of €500 per article currently quoted by SciPost (n.d.) and the €570 (\$650) per article costs estimated by Grossmann and Brembs (2020) for a conventional pre-publication peer-reviewed journal (not necessarily diamond OA) publishing 100 to 1,000 articles per year, with production services outsourced at market prices and all editorial duties performed by in-house staff.

³ <https://orion-dbs.community/>

Other estimations are higher: a more recent white paper on the Society Publishers' Coalition (SocPC) reported the median cost per publication across their members at €840 (£ 730) (Digital Science, 2023). While not limited to diamond journals, this estimate explicitly excludes any surplus. In his report 'Scenario modelling for Open Research Europe', Rob Johnson of ResearchConsulting sets article production costs at €650 per article, but arrives at total cost per article exceeding €2000 when costs for marketing, platform development and maintenance, and salaried editorial and production staff are added (Johnson, 2023). This range in estimates is significant and makes identifying a useful per article cost figure difficult.

Data on publishing agreements

With respect to publishing agreements there are two kinds of necessary data: information on the costs incurred by research organizations or consortia, and information on whether specific outputs were covered within an agreement. Ideally information on all costs would be based on actual payments and the services they relate to, rather than what is recorded in agreements as these can differ significantly. For a full analysis the division of costs into "read" and "publish" elements is also necessary. In our work we used aggregate figures at the consortial level, although more detailed data (by publisher and by organisation) clearly allows for more granular analysis, particularly in tracking value for money provided by agreements with specific publishers.

The ESAC registry⁴ is an important repository for tracking open access publishing agreements. Consortia and individual institutions registering their publishing agreements can include a link to the full-text agreement (redacted or not). The cOAlitionS Journal Checker Tool⁵ (JCT) collects further information about the institutions and journals that make up the agreement. The combined data can be used to link publishers, journals and research organisations that have access to specific agreements. Again, the coverage is not comprehensive and it varies across countries. The agreements registered generally provide useful metadata but information on agreed payments is much less complete, limiting the ability for financial analysis. In our analysis, while it is possible to use ESAC/JCT data to infer the potential inclusion of articles within publishing agreements, this does not enable reliable automated assessment of agreement coverage at the level of individual articles (see results).

Outside of ESAC and JCT there is some reporting by consortia, in most cases not structured or formalised, that provides information on the details of agreements. This is generally based on reporting by publishers to consortia. In a few settings, with Sweden as an exemplar, detailed public financial information on expenditures at the publisher level, is combined with public

⁴ ESAC, now part of OA Forward, (<https://esac-initiative.org>) and the Registry (<https://esac-initiative.org/about/transformative-agreements/agreement-registry/>)

⁵ <https://journalcheckertool.org>

release of contract details, providing the ability to quantify and categorise expenditures. However this is rare.

As a result, identifying whether a specific output is covered by an identified agreement remains a challenge. As noted we identified in our work that it was necessary to use “ground truth” data on the set of outputs covered by agreements. While this data is often provided to consortia by publishers, it is rare for it to be made public at the output level. Two exemplar cases where detailed data is made available publicly are the Swedish Bibsam consortium⁶ and the Council of Australasian University Librarians (CAUL) the purchasing consortium representing Australia and Aoteroa-New Zealand⁷.

Data on individual outputs can also be shared via the OpenAPC⁸ registry but as mentioned above, coverage here is limited and consortia level analysis requires a comprehensive dataset.

⁶ Bibsam data is shared on Github: https://github.com/Kungbib/oa-tskr/tree/master/Bibsam_artikeldata and the detailed financial data is contained in the annual reports <https://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:kb:publ-760> (in Swedish), details are also provided online at

<https://www.kb.se/for-bibliotekssektorn/eng/open-science/open-access/costs-of-scholarly-publishing.html>

⁷ CAUL data is available through a dashboard at

<https://public.tableau.com/app/profile/caul.office/viz/CAULReadPublishOAReporting/Summary>

⁸ <https://www.openapc.net>

METHODOLOGY

Our goal in this work was to develop a generalised approach to creating data-supported scenario models for future publishing systems costs at the consortial level. To do this we conducted analysis in three parts (see Figure 1).

Outline

Overall design

Gather outputs and build the publication profile.

Using a combination of OpenAlex and OpenAIRE we identify all outputs with an affiliation link to a set of Research Organization Registry (ROR) identifiers and combine data from multiple open data sources to identify OA status, pathways and locations, as well as discipline, publisher, and other characteristics

Construct a model of current costs

Using multiple sources we identify actual and inferred costs of publishing systems. This includes estimating list price APCs for all outputs, identifying which outputs were covered by agreements, assigning inferred costs to within agreement and out of agreement publishing with the goal of estimating average per article costs for articles in hybrid and pure open access journals, both within and outside agreements as well as identifying the proportion of articles in non-APC open access (“Diamond”) journals and available through repositories only.

Model future scenarios

We built a spreadsheet that allows the user to model potential scenarios at a high level. The spreadsheet uses a baseline of output counts and open access pathways from the bibliographic profiles and the per-article estimates of costs from the cost models. Scenarios are constructed by modifying 1) general parameters (output growth, increases in subscription and APC costs etc); 2) target parameters for future profiles for open access; 3) target parameters for inclusion of outputs within agreements. The spreadsheet projects the output profile into the future and uses the financial parameters to estimate future costs.

Figure 1. Schematic workflow of open access trajectory modelling. Analysis is conducted in three parts, combining information on publications, expenditures and consortium-specific policy goals.

Overall workflow implementation

The full underlying workflow and visualisation pipeline are available on Codeberg⁹. The workflow for bibliographic analysis and initial modelling of current costs is implemented in Data Built Tool (dbt) an open source SQL management system implemented in Python¹⁰. The core workflow generates a combined table at the single output level that combines data from multiple sources. Google BigQuery is used as the database system for all queries. Visualisation and data aggregation is carried out using a custom Python library based on plotly. The final scenario modelling is implemented as a spreadsheet in Google Spreadsheets for ease of sharing and modification.

Datasources

We primarily use specific open data snapshots to allow for full reproducibility and audit. In addition, the use of full data snapshots (rather than targeted API calls) allows further modification of the dataset (e.g. adding output from additional organisations and correcting or adding specific variables) without compromising the integrity of the source dataset. Data snapshots are processed and ingested into Google BigQuery. All the primary datasets used for bibliographic analysis are made available through the ORION-DBs community or are uploaded as part of the analysis pipeline itself from CSV files (primarily data from the consortia themselves and the list of organisation RORs). See Table 1 for a full specification of all data sources. As these are data dumps they can be fully specified and therefore any downstream analysis should be repeatable to the level of providing identical results.

⁹ <https://codeberg.org/TwoBirds/dbt-cost-model>

¹⁰ DBT Core is the open source version of Data Build Tool <https://www.getdbt.com>

Table 1. Data sources used. Specification of data sources used, including snapshot date, license, source provider and the organisation that is making the dataset available on Google Big Query. Consortium-provided data on outputs included in agreements (where publicly available) are included in the code repository and ingested in Google Big Query as part of the workflow.

Name	Snapshot date	Provided by	Available in GBQ from	Metadata licence
Butler et al ¹¹	2024-06-12	ScholComLab	Sesame Open Science	CC0
Crossref	2026-01-31	Crossref	SUB Göttingen	no restrictions on reuse
DOAJ	2025-07-31	DOAJ	Sesame Open Science	CC BY-SA ¹²
GOA	2025-08-02	Walt Crawford / SPARC	Sesame Open Science	CC BY
Journal Checker Tool	2025-04-12	SUB Göttingen	Sesame Open Science	CC0
OpenAIRE	2026-01-31	OpenAIRE	Sesame Open Science	CC BY
OpenAlex	2026-02-02	OpenAlex	SUB Göttingen	CC0
OpenAPC	2025-08-03	OpenAPC	Sesame Open Science	CC0
Output data Bibsam	2025-09-01	National Library of Sweden	Code repository	unclear
Output data CAUL	2026-06-09	CAUL	Code repository	unclear

Gathering outputs and building the bibliographic profile

We commence our bibliographic analysis by constructing a corpus of research outputs. We first identify the set of organisations relevant to a specific analysis. In this work we have examined outputs from two separate corpuses as exemplars: one for the Bibsam consortium and one for the CAUL consortium. Each output corpus is constructed by identifying all objects in OpenAlex and OpenAIRE that are connected via an affiliation link to those RORs. A full list

¹¹ Butler et al (2024)

¹² Since November 2025, DOAJ releases its journal-level metadata under a public domain dedication/CC0, but at the time of download (2025-07-31) the data were licensed as CC-BY-SA (<https://web.archive.org/web/20250801222733/https://doaj.org/terms/>)

of Bibsam and CAUL member organisations with ROR IDs is visible as the tables named “stg_organizations” in the Caul¹³ and Bibsam¹⁴ project folders within the code repository.

This superset of outputs is used as the basis for the overall corpus. It is subsequently filtered to create a subset of DOIs (any registration agency) and Crossref DOIs that are identified by the type “journal-article” which is the primary basis for most of the in depth analyses. The corpus is further restricted to publication years 2015-2024, using Crossref ‘issued year’ (earliest of print and online publication) as primary filter and, for records without Crossref DOI, publication year in OpenAlex and/or OpenAIRE.

We connect the corpus to data available from Crossref (publication year, type, ISSN), OpenAlex, OpenAIRE, DOAJ and with an ISSN-to-ISSN-L mapping extracted from OpenAlex. At this stage of the project, all open access information (except APCs) is taken from OpenAlex and DOAJ, but this can be extended to also include (and compare) open access information from OpenAIRE.

Analysis is conducted in Google BigQuery using SQL to combine and aggregate data. Data is subsequently processed to CSV and used to generate specific visualisations using Python.

¹³ https://codeberg.org/TwoBirds/dbt-cost-model/src/branch/main/caul/seeds/stg_organizations.csv

¹⁴ https://codeberg.org/TwoBirds/dbt-cost-model/src/branch/main/bibsam/seeds/stg_organizations.csv

Constructing a model of current costs

The cost model design allows for the estimation of costs in different categories of outputs and publishing services, using both estimated APC list prices (per journal and year of publication, including zero APC for diamond journals) and costs associated with consortial or institutional publishing agreements (split by Read and Publish components where available).

The current cost model calculates costs for different categories of publications for a given consortium or institution, including all affiliated publications, the subset of publications with an affiliated corresponding author and the proportions of both sets of publications that are currently identified as publisher OA and/or part of a consortial/institutional publisher agreement.

From an aggregated collection of APC data (DOAJ, Crawford, Butler et al, OpenAPC, consortial data where available) we calculate the “best list price APC” for all outputs under analysis, regardless of their open access status (see Table 2).

Table 2. List price APC estimation. Estimated APC list prices per journal for each year of publication are estimated on the following basis of priority. Currency conversions are limited with EUR, USD, and CHF being treated as equal and GBP multiplied by 1.4. Other currencies are discarded in the current implementation.

Priority	Source	Description
1	Institutional / consortium data	If a list price is provided for that journal and the matching year, use the mean of those values (there can be more than one)
2	DOAJ / GOA / Butler	List price for the journal for the matching year, in this order of priority
3	OpenAPC	Where there are at least three occurrences for the matching year and the difference between highest and lowest is less than 20% of the mean, use the mean value for the journal for the matching year.
4	Same as 1-3	Where no data for the publication year, use data for the year matching the year prior to publication or the year after in the same order of priority (1-3)
5	Same as 1-3	Where no data for the publication year or adjacent years is available, use a weighted average of all values available (weights are 10, 8, 8, 6, 2 for institutional, DOAJ, GOA, Butler et al. and OpenAPC respectively).
6	Same as 1-2	Estimate a publisher-based average (per year)

For each category of publications, we then use this list price to estimate the total APCs for each category of outputs, as well as the total costs of publisher agreements (see Figure 2). Where we have projected costs or total payments for publishing agreements this allows us to compare agreement costs to the notional total of list price APCs for the same publications, which could be considered to represent costs ‘saved’ by these agreements.

Figure 2. Schematic flowchart of cost modelling. APC list prices per journal and year of publication are used to calculate total list price APC for different groups of affiliated publications. For publications covered by publisher agreements, these totals represent saved list price APCs.

Information on **coverage** in publisher agreements can be obtained in two ways:

- using data on journals and institutions included in ESAC-registered consortial/institutional agreements, provided via the cOAlitionS Journal Checker Tool. These data can then be combined with information on affiliation and corresponding author.
- using data provided by the institution/consortium on publications covered by publisher agreements, often representing publisher-reported data

Information on **costs** for publisher agreements (including split by Read and Publish components where available) can similarly be obtained in two ways

- using data from publicly available contracts exposed via the ESAC/JCT registry
- using data provided by the institution/consortium

For the analysis presented here only Bibsam provides public data relating to all these aspects. In the case of CAUL we have data on coverage of outputs by publishing agreements, and this allows us to compare inferred agreement status to ground-truth data for both consortia. However the assignment of actual costs within publishing agreements can only be made for Bibsam.

Modelling future scenarios

The basis for scenario models is a set of baseline parameters that we estimate for 2024 based on available data from the bibliographic profile and the cost model. The baseline model is modified year on year by a set of global parameters (e.g. output volume growth and price increases) and by specific target proportions of open access categories for 2030. Different scenarios are then modelled by selecting different target values. These are used to model the overall growth, proportions of open access categories over time and costs in different categories. The current model uses a proportion interpolation over the period projected and this can be modified.

Baseline values

The model uses various baseline values. Most of these are programmatically derived from the available data in the bibliographic profile and the current cost modelling described above¹⁵. Costs for the institutional repository and for subscriptions (apart from R&P deals) need to be sourced separately.

Table 3 lists the various baseline variables used, with explanatory notes on some of the baseline variables provided below:

- In downstream modelling, open access proportion per OA type is combined with proportion of corresponding authors (affiliated with the consortium/institution) per OA type, since the latter may differ per OA type. For this reason, the **proportion of corresponding authors per OA type** is included as a separate baseline value.
- By combining open access classification and the identification of articles as included in agreements (using consortium/institutional data as ground truth for the latter), the **proportion of gold and hybrid OA that is covered in agreements** is provided as baseline value. In downstream modelling, target values for both can be set as user-defined variables (see below).
- Using the “best list price APC” calculated for each output combined with open access classification, the average **gold/hybrid list APC** is calculated for gold OA (APC-based) and hybrid OA articles in the full corpus.

¹⁵ Baseline values are generated by the dbt model ‘costmodel_whole_trajectory_parameters’ (https://codeberg.org/TwoBirds/dbt-cost-model/src/branch/main/template/models/costmodel/costmodel_whole_trajectory_parameters.sql)

- Using costs of publishing agreements (if available from the consortium/institution), the average **gold/hybrid APC in agreements** is calculated as the cost of the ‘publish’ part of each agreement divided by the number of articles published under the agreement¹⁶.

Table 3. Baseline variables used in trajectory modelling.

Variable	Type	Description
publication volume	automatic	calculated from bibliographic analysis
open access proportion per OA type	automatic	calculated from bibliographic analysis
corresponding per OA type	automatic	calculated from bibliographic analysis
gold / hybrid coverage in agreements	automatic	calculated from bibliographic analysis
gold / hybrid list APC	automatic	calculated from bibliographic analysis and cost modelling
gold / hybrid APC in agreements	automatic	calculated from financial data on agreements
read costs in agreements	automatic	calculated from financial data on agreements
repository costs	manual	to be provided by institution
subscriptions	manual	to be provided by institution

User-defined parameters

A number of modelling parameters can be user-defined. These include both global parameters (for inflation, open access growth and repository investment) and scenario parameters, where target proportions of open access categories can be set.

Global parameters

There are five high level user-configurable fields that globally affect the model (Figure 3). These are the output volume growth - used to drive volume dependent estimates, the global growth in the proportion of open access, which is used to model future subscription costs, year on year increases in APC pricing (above underlying inflation, i.e. not including general currency inflation) which drives both APC estimates and agreement estimates, and increases in subscription pricing which is applied to the subscription estimates. We do not currently model currency inflation separately as a parameter, although this could be easily added. The logic for

¹⁶ Where no split is given between the publish- and read part of the agreement is provided, this equates to the ‘Publish and Read’ (PAR) fee.

not including it is that any prediction of inflation seems quixotic currently and it can be argued that it is incorporated into the price increase parameters if these are derived from experience or data. These parameters drive an underlying model of overall volume growth and APC and agreement cost increases across the different open access pathways. The final global parameter is growth in repository investment, used to model costs of repository mediated OA.

Volume Growth (per annum)	2.0%
Global OA Growth (per annum)	2.0%
APC Inflation (per annum)	5.0%
Subscription Inflation (per annum)	5.0%
Repository Investment (per annum)	0%

Figure 3. Trajectory modelling - global parameters

Scenario parameters

The second class of user-defined parameters are the target proportions of open access categories for 2030, for the subset of articles with corresponding authors, and coverage of gold and hybrid articles in agreements (Figure 4). These are used to create alternative scenarios, by for instance targeting a shift from APC-gold to non-APC gold or from hybrid to repository-based open access. These targets, together with the global parameters for volume growth and inflation, are then propagated across the set of years from 2026-2032 to calculate projected volumes and costs per year in each category. For 2025, only global parameters are applied, as any actions towards changing open access proportions would be expected to take effect from 2026 onwards. This choice of years reflects the development of the modelling approach in 2025, but can be adjusted for use in 2026 and later.

OPEN ACCESS PARAMETERS		2030 TARGET
Gold non-APC OA proportion		10%
Gold APC OA proportion		30%
Hybrid OA proportion		45%
Green Only		15%
Closed		0%

AGREEMENTS PARAMETERS		TARGET 2030
Gold OA covered by agreements		50.0%
Hybrid OA covered by agreement		85.0%

Figure 4. Trajectory modelling - scenario parameters

Scenario modelling

For each chosen scenario, the model generates graphs for projected proportions of open access categories over time (both in absolute and relative numbers), as well as the associated costs in different categories (APCs outside agreements, APC within agreements, subscription costs and repository costs), again both in absolute and relative numbers.

Unit prices are calculated for each year, based on the price increase parameters. The volume profile is then combined with pricing estimates (including projected price rises) to calculate overall costs in the categories of APC-open access, agreement based open access, subscriptions and underlying investment increases. Subscription costs are estimated based on multiplying the baseline (2024) estimate by the subscription growth parameter, modified by the global open access growth parameter.

Non-APC gold and repository-only access do not have a per-output cost assigned. A goal with both strategies could be considered to achieve volume-independent pricing through infrastructure investments. This means it would make more sense to consider these kinds of investments separately, rather than as per article costs. For this reason we have chosen to focus on how a shift to these models reduces overall costs for publishing and subscription services and what levels of funding that releases for investment in these alternative routes to open access.

We include the “repository investment” parameter to allow for modelling the redistribution of costs from publishers to internal systems. This could also represent investment in internal publishing infrastructures. A future development could be to incorporate one-off or short term investments in the model. This can currently be done by manually changing the cost figures in the spreadsheet.

Interactive version

An interactive version of the modelling is provided as a Google Spreadsheet¹⁷. The tab ‘Baselines’ lists the various baseline values used in the model. The other tabs in the spreadsheet represent actual modelling results (see Table 4).

In each tab, green cells contain the parameters that can be user-defined. In the tab ‘Sandbox’, these parameters can be adjusted at will to see the effect on the model. The other tabs represent example open access scenarios with preset parameters to model the scenarios outlined in Table 4. The parameters modelled here target 100% open access profiles. Similar scenarios can also be developed that target lower levels of open access and/or mixed approaches to reach those levels, by adjusting the target open access parameters.

¹⁷ https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1l3bvOr4oI_ON3kETbYSIZcuC-O1br8NAPWABSX3WpyY/copy

Table 4. Example future scenarios with a goal of 100% OA

Scenario	Description
0	Current OA strategy (only affected by inflation)
A100	Increase number and coverage of R&P deals to minimize APCs out of contract
B100	Decrease number of R&P deals and shift to paying APCs out of contract
C100	Switch from R&P deals to only full gold OA publishing deals - don't pay for hybrid APCs.
D100	Decrease number of R&P deals and shift focus to diamond OA
E100	Decrease number of R&P deals and shift focus to repository-based OA

RESULTS

Bibliographic profiles

Coverage and output types

OpenAIRE and OpenAlex identify non-overlapping sets of research outputs as being affiliated with either Bibsam and CAUL members (Figure 5). OpenAIRE identifies and links a larger set of outputs to consortium members, including a considerable number of non-Crossref DOIs. OpenAIRE also captures research outputs without DOIs, while OpenAlex did not actively do so until recently (research outputs without DOI prior to 2021 are in OpenAlex because they are inherited from Microsoft Academic Graph). OpenAlex also uniquely identifies some outputs and appears to capture and link outputs more quickly.

Figure 5. Contributions of OpenAlex and OpenAIRE to the overall corpora. Bibsam (left) and CAUL (right). Overlap is determined for DOIs only; OpenAIRE and OpenAlex IDs without DOI are not disambiguated.

For the set of outputs that is limited to Crossref journal articles only (Figure X), there is substantial but not complete overlap between the outputs identified in both OpenAlex and OpenAIRE. Thus, combining OpenAlex and OpenAIRE provides a maximised set of the journal articles linked with consortium members. The ability to combine these datasets at scale is a benefit of using complete copies of these data sources. We recommend this approach in general for those seeking to maximise coverage in analyses.

Figure 6. Contributions of OpenAlex and OpenAIRE to the corpora of Crossref journal articles. Bibsam (left) and CAUL (right).

One interesting aspect of difference between Bibsam and CAUL is the apparent coverage of outputs found only in OpenAIRE that do and do not have DOIs. Given the European origins of OpenAIRE it is not surprising that OpenAIRE has a broader set of diverse outputs collected for Swedish institutions. At the same time, the proportion of those outputs with and without DOIs might also suggest that CAUL outputs that are being captured are more systematically associated with persistent identifiers (PIDs), perhaps representing a greater maturity of PID initiatives, particularly in the Australian context.

This is consistent with the pattern of output types for the two consortia (Figure 7). Due to limitations in the metadata, output types are comprehensively available only for Crossref DOIs. The CAUL output set includes an increasing number of outputs with non-Crossref DOIs. These will primarily be DataCite DOIs and may represent a greater coverage of shared research data for CAUL in our analysis data. The coverage of dissertations appears greater for CAUL than for Bibsam, which may relate to the degree to which dissertations have been assigned DOIs in each context.

Figure 7. Output types for corpora outputs with DOIs. Bibsam (left) and CAUL (right). The corpus under consideration is restricted to those objects that have a DOI (from any registry) so that disambiguation of objects is clear.

Disciplines

There is substantial disciplinary diversity across Bibsam and CAUL members with broad based universities contrasting with technical or medical focused institutions, and institutions with a strong HSS focus (Figure 8). While there are changes over this time period there do not appear to be substantial changes in the disciplinary profiles within institutions or for either consortium overall. This provides some assurance that the health of specific disciplines has remained broadly constant over time in both countries (albeit that the classification of HSS subjects is very high level). This consistency is also helpful in analysing the development of open access over the past ten years and projecting it into the future as disciplinary differences remain broadly constant.

Publishers

The disciplinary diversity is mirrored in the publishers of each institution's journal articles (Figure 8). Elsevier, Springer and Wiley dominate overall, representing over half of some institutions' outputs. Institutions with a strong HASS representation are associated with a significant contribution by Informa (Taylor and Francis) and to some extent also Sage. Amongst full open access publishers MDPI is the largest contributor overall, but with some drop off in recent years, which may be associated with controversy over quality assurance standards. A similar pattern may be seen with Frontiers. For larger institutions and for the corpus overall there is a long tail of smaller publishers.

Figure 8. Disciplines of journal articles by consortium member. Bibsam (top) and CAUL (bottom). The topics classification of OpenAlex is used, taking the field code of the primary topic assigned to each journal article.

Figure 9. Publishers of journal articles by consortium member. Bibsam (top) and CAUL (bottom). Crossref member ID is used to identify publishers.

Open access levels and pathways

Open access categories can be defined in different ways in the model, to allow focus on specific aspects (e.g. repository-based OA) and different open access policies (e.g. regarding versions, licenses and in- or exclusion of bronze OA)¹⁸.

Overall levels and the development of pathways towards open access show significant differences across the two consortia (Figure 10). Overall levels of open access are lower for CAUL as a whole. The adoption of publishing agreements as a route to open access is visible for both consortia, primarily through a substantial increase in the level of “hybrid” open access (operationalised as open access at the publisher website in a journal that is not identified as full open access). This occurs earlier for Bibsam reflecting an earlier adoption and more gradual expansion of these agreements.

Figure 10. Open access levels and pathways. Bibsam (left) and CAUL (right). This figure shows an extended categorisation that privileges publishing pathways to open access.

The focus on publishing agreements is also visible using an alternative classification of open access pathways that emphasises the presence of copies in repositories (Figure 11). For both Bibsam and CAUL there has been an increase in outputs available through both publisher sites and repositories, but a contraction of the proportion available only through a repository. This “green only” element represents progress in disciplines and settings where publishing open access options are (perceived) to be more limited. For CAUL there is a rise in the proportion of outputs only available through publisher sites.

¹⁸ Open access policies also often address embargo periods. While Unpaywall used to have a variable ‘oa_date’ that made analysis of embargo periods possible (in particular for repository-based OA), this variable is no longer available in either Unpaywall or OpenAlex.

Figure 11. Alternative categorisation of Open access - emphasising the role of repositories and dual pathways. Bibsam (left) and CAUL (right).

These trends raise the question of whether repositories have been neglected, both as pathways for open access and in the context of ensuring leverage in publishing agreement negotiations. With read and publish agreements taking both financial and human resources, it is not surprising that the capacity of repository systems might remain static or even degrade.

We can combine data on open access status and location, with a knowledge of repository systems and their relationship with specific organisations to define whether an author’s home institution repository has a copy of an output. We can also distinguish between records that OpenAlex finds in a specific repository and those that also have an accessible full text copy (Figure 12, 13).

Figure 12. Detection of repository copies (full text or record-only) in the “home repository”. Bibsam (left) and CAUL (right).

Figure 13. Detection of repository copies (full text or record-only) in the “home repository”, by consortium member. Bibsam (top) and CAUL (bottom).

Across both Bibsam and CAUL, there are large differences between consortium members as to the capture of both full text and record-only outputs in the home repository. Based on our analysis thus far we believe that cases where OpenAlex identifies a record but does not identify a full text copy of the output represent metadata only records, but we cannot rule out that in some cases there may be embargoed copies.

There are limitations in our capacity to identify the home repository for some institutions, particularly when they are provided by third parties. We match on either the OpenAlex source ID of the repository linked to the home organization, or on URLs (including handle prefixes) that are provided as part of a record's 'locations' parameter, based on a manually created list of mappings to institutions.

Modelling current costs

Inferring agreement status of articles based on public data

A core component of the cost modelling is to be able to distinguish between cases where an open access output was covered by a publishing agreement and where an APC or other payment is likely to have been paid. In the future it would be valuable to assign other platform contributions. We have not identified data sources with sufficient coverage (either externally or from consortia themselves) to explore this as yet. [TSOSI](#) is a promising initiative in this regard.

We treat consortium data as the “ground truth” on the coverage of specific outputs by agreements. To infer agreement status from ESAC/JCT data we match specific agreements, with information on institution and year from the cOAlitionS Journal Checker Tool to specific outputs. We then query OpenAlex metadata for corresponding author status as a proxy for an output qualifying for agreement coverage. Issues that arise can include a mismatch between the start and end dates of agreements and the calendar year of recorded publication, as well as differences in the publication date used in our analysis and in consortium validation processes. In addition, data snapshots of the Journal Checker Tool data only contain information on agreements in place at that given moment, and thus information on agreements in earlier years can be expected to be incomplete. Furthermore, not all publisher agreements will be registered in ESAC, including those that are out of scope of ESAC (e.g. agreements with full gold OA publishers). The most significant issue is the coverage, completeness and accuracy of corresponding author status in OpenAlex. Affiliation links can also be an issue. For outputs only linked via OpenAIRE we are unable to confirm corresponding author status for the institution of interest.

Overall our analyses using ESAC/JCT and corresponding author data from OpenAlex have an accuracy of 81% (for Bibsam) and 84% (for CAUL) (Figure 14). While these data can be used to estimate agreement coverage at a high level, the significant number of false positives and false negatives indicates that at the level of specific outputs the combination of ESAC/JCT

data with affiliation and corresponding author links is currently less reliable. Consortium-provided data is currently required to underpin a precise calculation of cost per article within agreements and APCs outside of agreements. This underlines the value of publicly released consortium data to support system-wide analyses.

Figure 14. Contingency tables of articles covered by publisher agreements based on consortium provided data and ESAC/Journal Checker Tool data. Bibsam (left) and CAUL (right).

Assigning overall and per-article costs to specific categories

In the following we focus on the Bibsam case as we have access to per-publisher and overall reported publishing costs. The analysis will focus on the whole consortium case. While per-institution and per-publisher analysis is supported by the data there are significant uncertainties at that level of granularity that are better supported by knowledge of the specific context.

The estimated and actual aggregate costs across the Bibsam consortium for 2020 to 2024 are shown in Table 5. The total cost of estimated APCs is given for different categories of articles: all articles affiliated with a Bibsam institution, those where a Bibsam member is corresponding author (as a proxy of articles for which Bibsam is the responsible party for APC payment), all articles that are open access at the publisher website, and the combination of both. The latter provides an estimate of the total cost if all Bibsam open access through publishers was associated with payment of APCs. This can be combined with an estimate of the APCs *not* paid because articles were included in a publishing agreement. For Bibsam, because the coverage of agreements is high, payment of APCs outside agreements is likely to be rare and therefore these numbers are close in value.

Finally we can compare this to the total cost of agreements (for read and publish agreements). In the case of Bibsam we do not have detailed data on the publish and read components of these costs, so we provide here the total reported. As these include the costs of access to subscription content it is notable that in 2024 the total agreement costs (including read access) were less than the estimate of APCs saved through agreements.

Table 5. Total APC cost estimates by category for Bibsam by year of publication.

Publication Year	Estimated APCs All articles	Estimated APCs Corresponding articles	Estimated APCs Publisher OA articles	Estimated APCs Publisher OA and Corresponding	Agreement total estimated list price	Agreement costs Publish & Read
2024	€128,236,513	€65,884,799	€95,762,780	€55,749,813	€50,118,824	€46,694,802
2023	€112,559,202	€61,088,044	€81,774,728	€50,453,932	€42,631,989	€44,725,429
2022	€105,045,899	€56,913,148	€72,948,360	€45,150,674	€39,703,349	€42,060,827
2021	€109,256,059	€59,909,785	€72,212,472	€45,311,786	€35,585,792	€37,021,083
2020	€95,763,136	€53,113,421	€56,441,307	€35,650,982	€25,713,963	€35,083,191

For earlier years the overall amounts paid exceed the estimated amount saved. This can at least partially be explained by increasing coverage of agreements over time (both in number of agreements and e.g. in inclusion of full gold journals in agreements). For earlier years subscription access was likely a larger component of the overall costs. In practice, consortia and publishers often do not document the precise apportionment of costs to read and publish sides of agreements¹⁹. While this will play a role in the calculation of offers, negotiations ultimately focus on the overall services provided and overall charges.

This makes a detailed calculation of value for money or return on investment challenging. Any estimate of the per-article costs incurred in different categories is highly sensitive to those proportions and this parameter underpins the scenario projections. Understanding how best to estimate those proportions will be key to improving this analysis in the future.

Using the total estimated and reported cost per category, combined with the number of articles in each category allows a calculation of the average costs per article in each category (Table 6). From these data, one observation is the large increase in average APCs over the past 5 years. This can be influenced by changes in publication behaviour (e.g. a switch to publishing in journals charging higher APCs as an indirect result of publisher agreements). However, it also reflects a real increase in APCs over time that far exceeds inflation and puts further strain on

¹⁹ One reason for documenting the split in contracts is when different VAT levels are applied to read- and publish components.

the sustainability of current open access strategies for institutions and consortia.

In our data, average APCs per article for articles in publisher agreements are higher than for other categories. This might reflect the different article composition in this category, with publisher agreements predominantly covering hybrid journals from larger traditional publishers that have higher list APCs.

Table 6. Average APC cost estimates by category for Bibsam by year of publication.

Publication Year	Estimated cost per article All articles	Estimated cost per article Corresponding	Estimated cost per article Publisher OA	Estimated cost per article OA and Corresponding	Agreements average estimated list price	Agreements average cost per article
2024	€2,648	€2,576	€2,669	€2,648	€3,057	€2,848
2023	€2,420	€2,368	€2,419	€2,411	€2,840	€2,979
2022	€2,223	€2,184	€2,230	€2,229	€2,647	€2,804
2021	€2,260	€2,222	€2,245	€2,243	€2,658	€2,786
2020	€2,127	€2,113	€1,095	€2,120	€2,693	€3,675

Trajectory modelling

Below we describe six hypothetical scenarios, each extrapolating a specific strategy towards 100% open access. In each scenario, the open access target is modelled to be reached in 2030 (i.e. in a five-year period), with the projection continuing for two more years until 2032.

While in reality, scenarios will always be mixed, the single-scenario projections do provide useful projections for how costs would develop under each scenario. Development of publication volume and costs for each scenario for Bibsam are shown in Figure 15 and 16, respectively.

The scenarios modelled here target 100% open access profiles. Other scenarios can also be developed by adjusting the target open access parameters. This can include scenarios in which only the currently closed outputs are considered for interventions, scenarios in which 100% open access is not reached and scenarios where mixed approaches are used to reach the target open access levels.

An interactive version of the modelling, including the preset scenarios described here, is provided as a Google Spreadsheet (see Methodology).

O - Current OA strategy (only affected by inflation)

Projecting the current open access strategy forward, with only applying inflation parameters, results in an estimated cost increase of 66% by 2032 (compared to the total cost of €84M in 2024). The model is sensitive to the chosen values of the inflation parameters, as well as the accuracy of the baseline values, and assumes no changes in the proportions of corresponding authors over the time period considered.

A - Increase number and coverage of R&P deals

Read and publish deals are currently delivering on a lower per-output cost than APCs. Projecting those costs forward and expanding the coverage to 100% increases the modelled volume in the agreements and leads to an overall increase in costs of 89% (mostly because otherwise closed publications would now be covered under agreements). The model is sensitive to the initial levels of APC-based gold open access, any increases in no-APC gold, and levels of repository-based access used to back the system. It is also sensitive to the relative levels of hybrid and gold that move into agreements due to the (current) price differential seen between these in terms of list APC. On the base parameters the headline prediction usefully represents the potential savings compared to Scenario B.

B - Pay APCs out of contract

Compared to the previous scenario, the primary difference is that prices rise higher due to the relative savings made within agreements. Total projected costs increase with 81% in this model, assuming similar usage of APC-based open access publishing as in Scenario A to get to 100% OA. The sensitivities are quite similar with respect to other input parameters. Costs rise significantly based on an increase in volume and projected cost increases in APCs. A very significant shift in APC pricing, or a substantial and rapid shift towards zero APC publishing would be required to offset this.

C - Switch to only full gold OA publishing deals

The distinction between this scenario and the first one is a stronger shift specifically towards emphasising fully open access journals in agreements. Modelling will therefore be sensitive to the degree to which hybrid publication pathways shift towards gold, or accept payment of APCs as a consequence of publishing choice. This makes this scenario very sensitive in outcomes to the detail of choices in the target parameters.

The second major sensitivity is the degree to which a “shift to gold” also includes adoption of non-APC models. If the shift successfully persuades existing journals and publishers to move to non-APC models and/or the policy shift is successful in supporting author adoption of non-APC models then costs are substantially reduced. For a model in which there is a residue of 15% hybrid publication supported by APCs and an increase in diamond uptake to 15% the projected costs rise with 57% by 2032. That rises to 69% if there is limited uptake of diamond.

D/E - Shift focus to diamond OA and/or repository-based OA

Both of these scenarios involve a shift to models without a directly modelled per-output cost. In both cases they involve radical shifts in publishing practices and routes to open access. Both models share the overall pattern of reducing apparent costs with 51% compared to the current open access strategy. Shifting fully to zero APC publishing models from the current scenario is unlikely to be feasible but the model is useful to suggest how savings to support reinvestment could be made.

A large shift to diamond involves a challenging concerted shift of funding, capacity building and author-engagement which would be challenging, particularly on a five year time frame. It is also important to note that savings made arise later in the five-year period whereas the investments would need to be made up front.

Either path therefore requires a significant investment, although the timeframes and mechanisms might differ, and both would require effective coordination at consortium level. The required shift in author behaviour with respect to publishing could be smaller, as authors could continue to publish in the same journals. However, it would involve significant investment to support or encourage manuscript deposition as well as ensuring a legal basis for zero embargo repository access either through rights retention or secondary publishing rights (national copyright exemption). It would also require a significant communications strategy in the face of likely responses from publishers (e.g. ACS charges for “manuscript development” or restrictions on licensing).

Other models and scenarios

The models used to project future costs and scenarios allow for a wide range of parameters to be tested. Other scenarios that have been examined included scenarios in which only the currently closed outputs were considered for interventions and scenarios in which 100% open access was not reached. Some of these scenarios are presented as mixed models in the scenario spreadsheet.

O - Current OA strategy

A - Expand agreements, reduce APCs

B - Reduce agreements, shift to APCs

C - Focus agreements on gold, no hybrid APCs

D - Focus on diamond, reduce agreements

E - Focus on green, reduce agreements

Figure 15. Main OA scenarios - proportions of open access categories over time. Publication volume for outputs of corresponding authors affiliated with Bibsam members. Open access categories: Gold non-APC (light blue), Gold APC (light yellow), Hybrid (light orange), Green only (light green), Closed (grey).

O - Current OA strategy

A - Expand agreements, reduce APCs

B - Reduce agreements, shift to APCs

C - Focus agreements on gold, no hybrid APCs

D - Focus on diamond, reduce agreements

E - Focus on green, reduce agreements

Figure 16. Main OA scenarios - cost by category over time. Total and category costs in Euros for each scenario covering outputs of corresponding authors affiliated with Bibsam members. Categories: Internal/Repository/Capacity (green), Subscriptions (blue), Agreements (yellow), APCs out of agreements (red).

DISCUSSION

There remains a significant need for strategic and forward-looking analysis of the scholarly communications systems. This is particularly the case for planning for future financial scenarios. Our goal with this work was to explore two parallel questions. What is our current capability in terms of building detailed data-driven financial models that can support scenario planning and what are the gaps and opportunities in the data landscape underpinning such work. Specifically we were interested in the qualities of publicly available data to enable this kind of modelling.

We were successful in building a public data driven system for detailed publication profiles based on groups of organisations identified by RORs. Existing open research information sources, particularly when used in combination, can deliver detailed and granular information on publishing activities and qualities. Public data on APCs and service charges for publishing remains more patchy but it is increasingly possible to undertake large scale and comprehensive analysis using available data. Again, the capacity to combine multiple data sources here is very valuable.

The specifics of the financial model depend on information on expenditures. Any more detailed analysis (especially at the level of individual institutions and/or publishers) would of course require more detailed information. The Swedish Bibsam consortium is an exemplar in regards to transparency with detailed expenditure information made publicly available. In addition, publicly available detailed information on the coverage of specific outputs by open access publishing agreements managed by Bibsam was valuable, both as a means of validating other approaches and as a ground truth that could be reliably used to support cost modelling.

Limitations and opportunities

The current analysis has a range of limitations, but also opportunities for expansion. A deliberate design choice was to keep the modelled scenarios simple. The intention was to support experts in a specific context to be able to understand the *range* of possible outcomes for specific scenarios. This is supported by surfacing the parameters used to drive the scenarios and making them adjustable in a familiar spreadsheet format. This led us to keep the implementation of the forward scenarios extremely simple.

This means that many aspects of the forward trajectory are modeled in a simplified fashion. Aspects like separately modelling currency inflation, or modelling changes in author behaviour that might surface as changes in the proportions of corresponding authors for different classes of open access were intentionally left out. A much more sophisticated model with many more options could be built into a dashboard or analytics system in the future. At the present time

we felt that current user needs were better served by a simpler and more easily understandable model.

A specific area that could benefit from more detailed modelling is the costs associated with investing in both repositories and other publishing infrastructures. Our findings emphasise that systems where costs rise linearly with publishing volume are not likely to be sustainable in the medium term. We therefore did not want to implement any estimates of “per article cost” for repositories or publishing platforms, including for no-APC (“diamond”) open access, but rather to support consideration of how savings made elsewhere could be reinvested. An obvious extension would be to provide for models of investment built on strategic plans. Currently this can be done by manually placing forward estimates into the spreadsheet but this is not explicit. A related extension could be to create a separate category for costs for Subscribe2Open, if these are viewed as a switch from subscription to no-APC open access costs.

The current model is built exclusively on information relating to journal articles with Crossref DOIs. We have not sought to expand on this due to the limited information available on the costs of publishing other types of outputs and the lack of structured information on them. The coverage of non-journal outputs in bibliographic databases is also less complete. Although this is improving and a growing set of such outputs are now indexed in open research information sources the coverage of key metadata elements such as affiliations is less complete, and matching information from different data sources is harder to do at the level of individual outputs without the use of DOIs. The underlying data model in our system can support additions through the addition of other open access pathways so this can be expanded in the future as more data becomes available.

Even within the journal space one specific challenge is the identification of journals. While ISSNs are widely used as identifiers, the current provision of journal metadata from the ISSN International Portal²⁰ does not facilitate the effective use of linking ISSNs for mapping between sets of ISSNs. The authoritative data from the ISSN International Portal is not made publicly available under an open license. Further, the quality of mappings available is fairly poor. In this work we used the ISSN-L mapping held by OpenAlex, but preferably we would use PIDs and metadata from the authoritative source Combined with errors in ISSNs in other datasets, in part due to the lack of technical systems to support validation of ISSNs, there remain issues in our datasets with coverage and data quality with respect to mapping the identity of journals. There would be value in work on robust “container identifiers” that are technically fit for purpose and designed with scholarly communications use cases in mind.

²⁰ issn.org

Design choices and user interfaces

Currently the scenario modelling consists of three elements. A database workflow implemented in Data Build Tool (dbt) using Google BigQuery as the database system; a visualisation library built in python using the plotly visualisation library that automatically pulls data from the tables created by dbt to flexibly produce graphs; and a spreadsheet that generates the financial models for the specified scenarios.

Our choice of Google Bigquery is a pragmatic choice, as source data is available through the ORION-DBs community that we helped to initiate. The logic of using Google BigQuery despite it being a corporate and non-open source system has been detailed elsewhere (Neylon et al., 2026). The use of dbt which provides an interface which is largely database agnostic allows for future flexibility, including different cloud or hosted database backends (commercial offerings or hosted Postgres SQL and others) as well as offering a pathway to local compute (using e.g. sqlite or DuckDB). While the SQL dialect would need to be adapted in the shift to other database systems the underlying workflow can be transferred directly. The use of dbt also makes the code more reusable providing for tests and documentation to be generated directly from the queries themselves. We have implemented the core SQL workflow as a dbt package which is then used for specific projects, in this case one for each consortium.

While much of the database workflow is automated there are a few elements that involve manual intervention. The first of these is identifying organisations by ROR. This is a central step in defining the scope of analysis. Within the publication profile workflow we currently also manually define the set of recognised repositories and their links to organisations. The quality of information to support these links is rapidly improving but in the current analysis we felt manual intervention remains necessary. Finally, because individual consortia have presented their agreement output data in different forms there is some modification of the table format required. For all three cases we currently implement the workflow with a CSV file used as a “seed” to generate an initial table that maps closely to the source data, alongside a “staging” query which converts that initial table to the core format. This is intended to provide a flexible approach that captures source data in its initial form while providing a straightforward method to convert it to an interoperable format.

The graphing library is based on the concept of categories. For any given graph, categories can be used as the division of vertical bar graphs or as the unit of analysis visualised as the panels in a graph set. As an example the full set of graphs in the data and code repository includes open access by publisher for each consortium²¹. Any of the categories used as divisions in the bar

²¹ The relevant graphs for open access by publisher, using the “extended” open access type as categories can be found at https://codeberg.org/TwoBirds/dbt-cost-model/src/branch/main/caul/project_graphs/graphs/oa_categories/oa_extended_model/oa_by_publisher_oa_extended_model_pct.png for CAUL and https://codeberg.org/TwoBirds/dbt-cost-model/src/branch/main/bibsam/project_graphs/graphs/oa_categories/oa_extended_model/oa_by_publisher_oa_extended_model_pct.png (for Bibsam)

chart (publication type, open access category, publisher, discipline) can also be used as panels and vice versa. This functionality leverages the structure of the key bibliographic table. For each graph a query is generated and the data downloaded to the local system (which can then be used to generate graphs without further queries required). The library for this is also included in the dbt package as the two are tightly coupled. In the medium term our goal is to expand this library and to work towards easy-to-use systems that allow production of similarly structured tables to draw from.

Overall our goal was to balance the commitment to open source and transparency in practical terms. We believe the use of Google BigQuery while preserving an exit strategy and the capacity to share the explicit underlying code (both queries and visualisation code) in an open source form strikes a good balance with flexibility for future developments.

Conclusions

We have shown that it is possible to do large scale modelling and analysis of the complexities of the publication system using public data. Some parts of this system are well supported by open research information and can be expanded easily to other settings. Specifically the bibliographic profiles can be produced for any set of organisations in a largely automated fashion. Analysis of inclusion in publishing agreements is possible with data in the public domain in many cases but coverage is less complete. In our analysis the detailed output-level data provided by Bibsam and CAUL was invaluable.

Financial analysis depends on access to cost or expenditure information. This was only available in a public form for Bibsam. Other consortia do collect this data and we have used internally available, but confidential data in other analysis. The analysis system itself does not require that data be openly available. This illustrates an important aspect of open research information, that it facilitates straightforward combination with confidential data because its use is not limited and it can be deployed in secure systems that preserve that confidentiality and security.

It is our belief that there is substantial value in making this financial data more public and transparent, as it can support comparison, discussion and critique. The strategic considerations for future scholarly communications investments is contentious and this makes full transparency challenging. Nonetheless where data is shared it helps us to build a picture of global investments and plan as a community for the future. We commend Bibsam and CAUL for their commitments to transparency and sharing experiences and hope this can encourage consortia to have the confidence to release more information. We also look forward to the wider uptake of projects such as openCost and others providing frameworks for the effective sharing of financial information.

Finally, this analysis addresses one specific concern in the scholarly communications ecosystem that can be addressed with data-driven evidence. More broadly it shows the opportunities for strategic analysis derived from existing open research information resources, and the value that can be derived from linking those to other relevant data sources. The future for rich, strategic analysis is very promising.

CODE AND DATA AVAILABILITY

The main public data used as primary sources is detailed in Table 1. All code, including SQL templates, configuration files, the python visualisation library and resulting graph images and aggregate CSV files supporting them are available at

<https://codeberg.org/TwoBirds/dbt-cost-model>

All intermediate tables generated by the code (including all record-level tables) are available in Google Big Query:

https://console.cloud.google.com/bigquery?ws=!1m4!1m3!3m2!1ssos-project-space!2sBibsam_2026 (Bibsam)

https://console.cloud.google.com/bigquery?ws=!1m4!1m3!3m2!1stwobirds-463608!2scaul_2026 (CAUL)

An interactive version of the trajectory modelling, including baseline values and preset parameters for the OA scenarios described in this paper, is available as Google Spreadsheet (for Bibsam):

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/113bvOr4oI_ON3kETbYSIZcuC-O1br8NApWABSX3WpyY/copy

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